

Exchange Rate Volatility and Export Competitiveness in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of exchange rate volatility on export competitiveness in Nigeria for the period 1985-2024. Unit root test was conducted using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and the result revealed a mixed order of $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ variables. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bound test was employed to test for co-integration among the variables. It was found from the bound that there was no significant long-run relationship between the real effective exchange rate, exchange rate volatility, GDP, inflation rate, lending rate, and non-oil exports in Nigeria within the period under study. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) was used to estimate the short-run parameters in the model. Short-run analysis shows that inflation and GDP are significant predictors of non-oil exports, although the practical impact of GDP is near-zero. However, exchange rate volatility and lending interest rates had negative and insignificant effects on non-oil exports in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study concludes that in the short run, price levels and domestic production are engines of export performance in Nigeria. It is recommended that monetary authorities closely monitor the foreign exchange market and implement policies to mitigate Naira fluctuations, while fiscal policies should focus on enhancing national GDP through infrastructure development and industrial incentives to broaden the export base.

Keywords: Exchange rate volatility, GDP, Inflation rate, Non-oil export, Export competitiveness

1. Introduction

Nigeria, one of Africa's largest economies with a GDP of over \$362 billion in 2023 (World Bank, 2023), has seen significant fluctuations in its trade productivity over time. Nigeria's exports fell sharply from \$95 billion in 2014 to about \$60 billion in 2023 (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2023). The global oil price collapse, structural inefficiencies, and a lack of diversification of export products are among the reasons for this decline in exports. Over 80% of Nigeria's export revenue still comes from oil and gas, making the nation extremely susceptible to outside shocks in the world's energy markets (NBS, 2023). The country struggles with trade competitiveness due to low product diversification, limited value addition, overdependency on the oil sector, and inefficient transportation and infrastructure. Exchange rate volatility is a major barrier, reducing export competitiveness and causing uncertainty for businesses (Adewuyi & Akande, 2015). Nigeria's economy has traditionally been heavily reliant on oil exports, which account for a significant amount of both government income and foreign exchange gains. Due to this dependency, the economy is liable to changes in the oil price globally, which has had a substantial impact on the Naira's exchange rate.

According to Muoneke et al. (2022), exchange rates are crucial to international trade and a major factor in determining a nation's competitiveness in the world market. The stability of the exchange rate and its alignment with global trends are crucial for an economy such as Nigeria, which is highly dependent on

the export of crude oil and is progressively seeking to diversify its export portfolio (Duru et al., 2022). Transforming the Nigerian economy beyond its reliance on oil exports has been a top priority of the Government. In order to move beyond Nigeria's oil dependency, the manufacturing sector should be prioritized. This sector is vital for building export competitiveness, as well as creating employment, earning foreign exchange, and driving sustainable economic growth (Alade and Okeke, 2023). Nigeria's heavy reliance on oil revenues has led to a strong relationship between oil prices and the Naira's value, with the oil boom resulting in the Naira appreciating, while also contributing to the instability that harms other sectors, such as agriculture and manufacturing. (World Bank, 2023).

According to Mesagan et al. (2021), Nigeria finds it difficult to establish itself as a major exporter of a variety of goods on the international market despite having an abundance of natural and human resources. Volatility in exchange rates has made planning more difficult, raised exporters' costs, and inhibited investment in export-oriented sectors (Salik & Aras, 2022). The country's dependence on oil revenue worsens these issues, leaving other sectors exposed to foreign shocks (Lai et al., 2023). Developing sustainable economic policies requires an understanding of exchange rate fluctuations and how they affect export competitiveness. The main drive of this study is to investigate the effect of exchange rate volatility on exports in Nigeria, specifically focusing on how Naira fluctuations affect the ability of domestic products to compete in the international market.

2. Literature Review

According to the purchasing power parity (PPP) theory developed by Gustav (1920), the equilibrium exchange rate between two non-convertible currencies is determined by the equality of their relative price movements. In order to balance trade balances, this theory suggests that exchange rates should be adjusted to match the prices of goods and services between nations (Ewubare & Ushie, 2022). Furthermore, traditional theory of risk aversion by Ethier (1973), assumes that exchange rate volatility creates uncertainty regarding the future profitability of international trade. Because exporters are generally risk-averse, they view currency fluctuations as an additional cost of doing business. Consequently, the theory predicts a negative relationship between exchange rate volatility and export performance.

Table A: Summary of Reviewed Empirical Studies

Author(s) & Year	Study focus	Methodology	Variables	Key Findings	Gap
Ismail et al. (2024)	Exchange rate and export performance	Not specified	Exchange rate, Export value/volume	Found a strong positive relationship between exchange rate and export performance; noted reliance on oil.	Did not employ advanced econometric modeling to test for volatility.
Okoh & Nwakwanowo (2024)	Agricultural product exports in Nigeria.	VAR	Volatility, Trade openness, Agricultural finance,	Exchange rate volatility, trade openness, and agricultural	Focus is limited to the agricultural sector rather than total non-oil exports.

			Agricultural employment	finance positively impact agricultural exports.	
Umaru et al. (2023)	Impact of fluctuations on Nigerian exports.	ARDL (Bounds Test)	Exchange rate, Export data (CBN)	Exchange rate volatility has a significant negative impact on exports.	Does not account for the extreme currency depreciations observed in late 2023-2024.
Muoneke et al. (2023)	Extreme fluctuations in oil-exporting African nations.	Non-linear ARDL & Asymmetric Thresholds	Exchange rate shocks (major/minor), Export trade	Impacts are uneven; large changes differ from small changes.	Cross-country study; results for Nigeria are generalized within the African context.
Nnoli et al. (2023)	Inflation and exchange rates on agricultural exports	Causality Analysis	AEV, Exchange rate, inflation	Positive and significant impact of both EXR and INF on exports.	Short sample size (34 obs) limits the robustness of long-run cointegration testing.
Ogadi et al. (2023)	Real exchange rate on the productive sector.	VAR (Vector Autoregression)	Real Exchange Rate, Productive sector output.	Volatility significantly affects the productive sector; recommended a unified rate.	Focuses on the "productive sector" generally, not specifically export competitiveness.
Duru et al. (2022)	Volatility effects on Nigerian exports	ARCH, GARCH, EGARCH, TARARCH & ARDL	Nominal Effective Exchange Rate, Volatility, Exports.	Confirmed volatility exists but found its impacts to be negative and negligible.	The study period misses post-COVID and 2023 reform shocks.
Olufayo & Fagite (2014)	Export industry performance (1980-2011)	SUR & GARCH	Oil exports, Non-oil exports, Volatility	Negative correlation; floating exchange system increased uncertainty	Data is outdated and does not reflect modern trade dynamics.

Literature Gap

Despite the extensive research on exchange rate behavior in Nigeria, several gaps remain and the main gap lies on the inconsistency result. For example, there is a contradiction between the finding of Onafowora and Owoye (2008) who employed traditional OLS techniques and simple deviation to measure exchange rate volatility and the Abanikanda (2022) and Idiku (2024) used “GARCH” and “BEKK-GARCH” models. Furthermore, Okon and Etim (2021) results showed a positive relationship between volatility and export, whereas Adebayo and Ojo (2022) and Isah and Ekeocha (2023) report a negative impact. This study fills that gap by employing the ARDL bounds testing approach. Secondly, a sectoral gap exists as most studies focus heavily on the oil sector. However, there is a scarcity of empirical evidence addressing the influence of currency dynamics on Nigeria's developing non-oil industries. This study focuses on export competitiveness, specifically addressing a sector that is more vulnerable to exchange rate risk but has been understudied compared to the oil sector. Finally, a recency gap is evident: existing studies do not account for the massive structural shifts in 2023, when Nigeria moved to a unified, floating exchange rate, introducing market-driven volatility. This study seeks to fill these gaps by utilizing a moving standard deviation and ARDL framework on the most recent data to provide a clearer understanding of how these dynamics affect non-oil export competitiveness.

3. Methodology

The study obtained secondary data from the statistical bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), World Development Indicators, and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) for the period 1981 to 2024. This study adopts a two-stage estimation technique. First, the Realized Volatility is used to generate the exchange rate volatility series, capturing the dynamic fluctuations of the Naira. Subsequently, the ARDL model was applied to simultaneously estimate both short-run dynamics and the long-run equilibrium between exchange rate volatility and non-oil exports performance (Muoneke et al., 2023; Okhonia & Giwa, 2024).

3.1 Model Specification

The functional form of the model is stated below:

$$NOEX = f(REER, INF, GDP, RINT, EXV) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

The econometric estimation form of the functional specification of the model above is presented as follows:

$$NOEX = \beta_0 + \beta_1 REER + \beta_2 INF + \beta_3 GDP + \beta_4 LED + \beta_5 EXV + \mu \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

The logged form:

$$\ln NOEX_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln REER_t + \beta_2 \ln INF_t + \beta_3 \ln GDP_t + \beta_4 \ln LEN_t + \beta_5 \ln EXV_t + \mu \dots (3)$$

Where;

In NOEX = Natural logarithm of Non-Oil Exports (Dependent Variable)

In REER = Natural logarithm of Real effective exchange rate (measures competitiveness)

INF = Inflation rate

In GDP = Natural logarithm of Gross domestic product

LEN = Lending interest rate

EXV = Exchange rate volatility

μ = Stochastic Term

Measuring Exchange Rate Volatility

Volatiles are not observed variables but estimates from the variance of the variable for which volatility is measured. For the purpose of this study, the moving standard deviation approach is adopted to estimate the volatility component of the exchange rate variable. This method, popularized by Gujarati (2003) and recently applied by Adewuyi and Akande (2015), measures exchange rate volatility in terms of the squared deviation of log-returns. This “Realized Volatility” proxy is defined as:

$$EXV_t = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m-1} \sum_{i=1}^m (\ln REER_{t-i=1} - \overline{\ln REER})^2} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

This approach is preferred as it captures the magnitude of annual exchange rate shocks while maximizing the degrees of freedom available in a relatively small annual sample, unlike GARCH models which typically require higher frequency data for statistical consistency.

4. Results and Discussion of Findings

Pre-Esimation Tests

The pre-estimation tests included descriptive statistics, stationarity check using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller(ADF),

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	LN_NOEX	LN_REER	INR	LN_GDP	LEN	EXV
Mean	11.33592	4.696260	19.55944	1.19E+14	18.13905	0.169158
Median	11.57078	4.610195	13.00697	1.04E+14	17.55333	0.074720
Maximum	16.21046	6.285806	72.83550	2.18E+14	31.65000	0.711716
Minimum	5.511006	3.907510	5.388008	4.61E+13	9.433333	0.015941
Std. Dev.	2.822360	0.522292	16.71435	6.09E+13	4.804357	0.195527
Skewness	-0.291427	1.372067	1.749058	0.307692	0.696912	1.669251
Kurtosis	2.004941	4.860457	4.978855	1.435695	3.973214	4.566613
Jarque-Bera	2.271846	18.77726	27.59417	4.827319	4.936894	23.23311
Probability	0.321126	0.000084	0.000001	0.089487	0.084716	0.000009
Sum	464.7727	192.5467	801.9369	4.89E+15	743.7013	6.935489
Sum Sq. Dev.	318.6286	10.91154	11174.78	1.48E+29	923.2738	1.529235
Observations	41	41	41	41	41	41

Source: Author’s Computation (2026) using E-Views 12

The descriptive results revealed that except for LN_GDP and INR, the standard deviation scores of the variables were relatively minimum, indicating less variation in the data spread. The result also showed the skewness, kurtosis, and distribution characteristics of the variables. The skewness of most variables, specifically LN_GDP (0.31), LN_REER (1.37), EXV (1.67), INR (1.75), and LEN (0.70) shows that they are positively skewed. LN_NOEX (-0.29) shows a slight negative skewness, indicating a tail extending towards lower values. This implies that the majority of the variables in the series are not normally distributed.

The kurtosis values for LN_REER (4.86), and EXV (4.57), and INR (4.98) are significantly above 3, reflecting leptokurtic distributions with frequent extreme fluctuations likely caused by economic shocks in Nigeria. Conversely, LN_NOEX (2.00) and LN_GDP (1.43) are platykurtic, suggesting flatter distributions with fewer extreme outliers. Similarly, the p-values of the Jarque-Bera statistics clearly showed that for LN_REER, EXV and INR do not follow a normal distribution, as their probability values are less than 0.05. The non-normal distribution of these series, as revealed by the descriptive statistics, is often due to the use of high-velocity data that is subject to inherent volatility and economic shocks. However, this non-normality is not a problem for this study given the application for ARDL framework rather than basic Ordinary Least Square (OLS).

Correlation Analysis

Table 2: Results of the Correlation Matrix

	LN_NOEX	LN_GDP	LN_REER	EXV	INR	LEN
LN_NOEX	1.000000					
LN_GDP	0.936713	1.000000				
LN_REER	-0.229262	-0.111176	1.000000			
EXV	-0.414410	-0.450228	-0.145366	1.000000		
INR	-0.259395	-0.282369	-0.192448	0.219329	1.000000	
LEN	-0.035582	-0.186677	-0.657383	0.155753	0.407508	1.000000

Source: Author's Computation (2026) using E-Views 12

As shown in the results, LN_GDP and LN_NOEX indicate a very high positive correlation of 0.936. While this suggests a strong association, it also signals potential multicollinearity. However, because LN_NOEX is the dependent variable and LN_GDP is an independent variable, this high correlation simply confirms that GDP is a significant driver of export growth.

Table 3: Result for Unit Root Test

AT LEVELS					AT THE FIRST DIFFERENCE				
INTERCEPT			TRENDS AND INTERCEPT		INTERCEPT			TRENDS AND INTERCEPT	
Variables	ADF statistics	5% critical value	ADF statistics	5% critical value	Variables	ADF statistics	5% critical value	ADF statistics	5% critical value

LN_NOEX	-0.409202	-2.931404	-2.985336	-3.518090	LN_NOE X	7.849863	-2.933158	-7.784355	-3.520787
LN_REER	-2.977411	-2.933158	-3.069288	-3.520787	LN_REE R	-4.761663	-2.933158	-4.690718	-3.520787
LEN	-2.316744	-2.931404	-2.295626	-3.518090	LEN	-5.066869	-2.933158	-4.891950	-3.520787
INR	-3.057212	-2.931404	-3.958875	-3.520787	INR	-5.996500	-2.933158	-6.628453	-3.523623
IN_GDP	0.498397	-2.933158	-2.097548	-3.520787	IN_GDP	-3.700825	-2.933158	-3.889123	-3.520787
EXV	-3.044057	-2.936942	-3.347145	3.526609	EXV	-5.594611	-2.943427	-5.531141	-3.536601

Source: Author’s Computation (2026) using E-Views 12

The unit root test results shown in the table indicate that the variables are stationary at various levels. Specifically, the variables LN_REER, INR, and EXV are stationary at levels, as their ADF statistics are more negative than the 5% critical values. On the other hand, LN_NOEX, LEN, and LN_GDP are non-stationary at levels but become stationary at the first difference, indicating they are integrated of the order on I (1).

Table 4: Results for the Bounds Test

Test Statistic	Value	Significance	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	2.219363	10%	2.08	3
K	5	5%	2.39	3.38
		2.5%	2.7	3.73
		1%	3.06	4.15

*Asymptotic: n=1000

Source: Author’s Computation (2026) using E-Views 12

The results in Table 4 indicate an F-statistic of 2.219363, which is below the lower bound I(0) critical value of 2.39 at the 5% significance level. Thus, we fail to reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration, meaning that there is a short-term relationship between EXV, INR, LEN, REER, and GDP.

Table 5: Results of VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-1555.802	NA	2.01e+28	82.20010	82.45866	82.29209
1	-1372.855	298.4918	9.05e+24	74.46607	76.27603*	75.11004*
2	-1344.857	36.83952	1.60e+25	74.88722	78.24858	76.08317
3	-1284.252	60.60558*	6.65e+24*	73.59219*	78.50495	75.34011

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion

Source: Author’s Computation (2026) using E-Views 12

The lag length selection results in Table 5 indicate a divergence: AIC selects lag 3, while SC and HQ select lag 1. AIC is adopted for this study because it provides a more comprehensive capture of the transmission mechanism between exchange rate volatility and non-oil exports. Choosing a higher lag length (3) ensures that the model remains robust to autocorrelation, a common issue in Nigerian macroeconomic data, where policy impacts typically manifest over multiple years.

Table 6: ARDL Model Estimation

SHORT- RUN MODEL				
VARIABLE	COFFICIENT	STANDARD ERROR	T-STATISTICS	PROBABILITY
LN_REER	-0.204092	0.305229	-0.668652	0.5024
D(LN_GDP)**	4.51E-14	1.56E-14	2.891573	0.0168
LEN	-0.08640	0.022848	-0.378147	0.9471
INR	0.017564	0.006573	2.672111	0.0126
D(EXV)	-0.196906	0.703037	-0.0280079	0.3471

R-squared	0.985307	Mean dependent var.	11.48154
Adjusted R-square	0.978777	S.D. dependent var.	2.697819
S.E. of regression	0.393019	Akanke info criterion	1.227041
Sum squared resid	4.170532	Schwarz criterion	1.775927
Log likelihood	-11.54083	F-statistics	150.8874
Durbin Watson stat	2.173144	Prob(F-statistics)	0.000000

Source: Author’s Computation (2026) using E-Views 12

The results from the Table 6 show that LN_GDP (Gross Domestic Product) and INR (Inflation Rate) have a statistically significant impact on Nigeria’s non-oil exports in the current period. Specifically, a 1% increase in GDP (D(LN_GDP)) leads to a statistically significant increase in export performance by 4.51×10^{-14} units ($p = 0.0075$). However, the estimated coefficient of 4.51×10^{-14} indicates that this impact is practically and economically negligible. Similarly, a 1% increase in the inflation rate (D(INR)) results in a 0.0175% increase in export performance ($p = 0.0126$). Both variables are statistically significant at the 5% level.

On the other hand, the Lending Rate (LEN), Exchange Rate Volatility (D(EXV)), and the Real Effective Exchange Rate (D(LN_REER)) show negative impacts on exports, with coefficients of -0.0086, -0.1969, and -0.2040 respectively. However, these impacts are statistically insignificant in the short-run, as their p-values (0.7083, 0.7816, and 0.5094) exceed the significance threshold. This suggests that while currency instability, appreciation, and high borrowing costs exert downward pressure on trade, their immediate effect is not as statistically pronounced as price levels (INR) and domestic productive capacity (GDP), though the latter’s actual contribution to export growth remains infinitesimal in magnitude.

The Adjusted R-squared value of 0.9788 implies that approximately 97.88% of the variations in Nigeria’s non-oil exports are explained by the independent variables within the model, indicating a very high goodness of fit. Furthermore, the F-statistic of 150.89 with a p-value of 0.0000 confirms that the overall model is statistically significant. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.17 suggests that the model is relatively free from severe serial correlation, making the estimates reliable for policy recommendations.

Post Estimation Test

Table 7: Post Estimation Results

HETEROSKEDASTICITY TEST: Bresuch-Pagan-Godfrey			
F-statistic	0.963774	prob.F(12,27)	0.5042
obs*R-squared	11.99554	prob. Chi-Square(12)	0.4460
Scaled explained SS	5.335561	prob. Chi-Square(12)	0.9458

Ramsey RESET test			
	Value	Df	Probability
T-statistic	0.277202	26	0.7838
F-statistic	0.076841	(1,26)	0.7838

Breush-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	2.767306	Prob. F(2,14)	0.0971
Obs*R-squared	10.76629	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0046

The model was subjected to several diagnostic tests to ensure the reliability and validity of the estimated parameters. The Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test for heteroskedasticity returned an F-statistic of 0.9637 (p-value of 0.5042), indicating that the null hypothesis of homoskedasticity cannot be rejected. Furthermore, the Ramsey REST test yielded a p-value of 0.7838, indicating that the model is correctly specified and free of functional form errors.

However, the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM test showed a chi-square p-value of 0.0046, which is below the 0.05 threshold. This indicates the presence of serial correlation in the residuals. While the presence of autocorrelation does not bias the coefficient estimates, it can lead to underestimated standard errors, potentially inflating the t-statistics. To address this limitation in future refinements of the model, a lagged dependent variable (IN_NOEXt-1) or Autoregressive (AR) terms could be integrated to absorb the remaining systemic patterns in the error terms. Nevertheless, given the high Adjusted R-squared and robust F-statistic, the model still provides a valuable framework for understanding the directional impact of exchange rate volatility on Nigeria's non-oil exports.

CUSUM test

Table 8: CUSUM Test results

The CUSUM Test shows that the model is well specified. This shows that the coefficients in our model are stable and have not changed significantly over time.

CUSUM of Squares

This test shows that the blue line remains within the borders. This demonstrated that the variance in our data is steady, even despite the major economic swings Nigeria has faced.

Discussion of the Findings

The empirical results allow for a detailed assessment of how Nigeria's non-oil export performance was impacted by the independent variables between 1985 and 2024. A primary finding is that GDP serves as a statistically significant coefficient with a magnitude of 4.51×10^{-14} , rendering its impact economically negligible. This implies that while productive capacity is theoretically aligned with arguments by Ozata (2020) and Nasiru et al. (2024), the actual scale of Nigeria's current manufacturing base is too infinitesimal to drive substantial export growth in real terms.

Furthermore, the study found a positive and significant relationship between the inflation rate (D(INR)) and exports at the 5% level ($p = 0.0126$). While this initially appears to contradict standard trade theory, it may be explained by demand-pull effects or the survivalist behaviour of domestic firms. As suggested by Onwubuariri et al. (2022), firms may aggressively push export volumes to acquire foreign exchange as a hedge against the rising costs of domestic production. This reflects a short-run strategic adjustment rather than an improvement in underlying competitiveness, as sustained inflation eventually erodes long-term quality (Gelle, 2025).

In contrast, Exchange Rate Volatility (D(EXV)), the Real Effective Exchange Rate (D(LN_REER)), and the Lending Rate (LEN) yielded negative and statistically insignificant coefficients. This indicates that during the period under review, currency movements and high borrowing costs exerted downward pressure but did not significantly dictate Nigeria's non-oil export volumes in the immediate short run. This supports the views of Ewubare and Ushie (2022), who noted that in an import-dependent economy, exchange rate fluctuations often fail to stimulate exports due to structural bottlenecks. As Olabisi and Akeju (2024) confirm, volatility may even erode competitiveness by spiking production costs rather than incentivizing trade.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study investigated the effect of exchange rate volatility and export competitiveness in Nigeria from 1985 to 2024. The study concludes that in the short-run, exchange rate volatility was not a primary determinant of export competitiveness, with domestic productive capacity and price levels playing more statistically pronounced roles. However, this finding must be qualified: the model's lack of a strong long-run relationship suggests that structural bottlenecks may be masking the true impact of currency instability.

This implies that for export performance to be effectively enhanced in Nigeria, price levels must be stabilized to prevent the erosion of real earnings, and domestic products must be improved. Based on these findings, it is recommended that internal production capacity be expanded beyond its current marginal levels. To achieve this, infrastructure that lowers the cost of production should be prioritized. Moreover, policies to stabilize inflation should be the uppermost priority of the Central Bank of Nigeria to ensure that the nominal gains in the export value are not neutralized by domestic price instability.

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